

Dipole Moments of Some Non-Benzenoids Calculated by Self-Consistent ω -technique

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Dipole moments of some non-benzenoids have been calculated by a self-consistent ω -technique. The results obtained are better than those obtained by the conventional ω -technique and are comparable to those obtained by more sophisticated methods.

SOME very interesting analyses have recently been made on the convergence of the ω -technique¹⁻⁴.

We have shown earlier that the conventional ω -technique is actually in error¹, and not just slowly convergent as maintained by Harris⁴, because of the neglect of the charge dependence of the coulomb integrals while minimising the energy of a system. The neglect of charge dependence during minimization leads to charge distributions which are not strictly self-consistent. In what follows we give the method of self-consistent ω -technique in brief referring elsewhere¹ for further detail and, apply the method for the calculation of dipole moments of some non-benzenoids.

Method of Calculation :

The pi-electron energy (E) of an even electron system is given by $E = 2\text{tr}HR$ (1)

where $H_{rr} = \alpha_0 + \omega\beta_0(1 - 2R_{rr})$
 $H_{rs} = \beta_0$, where r and s are neighbours
= 0, otherwise

α_0 and β_0 are standard coulomb and resonance integrals respectively and ω is a dimensionless constant the value of which is usually taken as 1.¹ to provide a best fit with the observed and calculated ionization potentials. The R matrix is defined as equal to TT^+ where the LCAO coefficients of respective MO's are collected in the columns of the T matrix. $2R$ then gives the charge and bond order matrix.

A first order variation in energy, maintaining the idempotency of R, leads to

$$E = 4\text{tr} [(1-R)WR]^+ \Delta \quad \dots (2)$$

where Δ is an arbitrary non-singular matrix and $W = H + D$ with

$$D_{ij} = -2 \omega\beta_0 R_{ij} \delta_{ij}$$

At the minimum ($\delta E = 0$), being arbitrary, we have
 $WR = RWR$

or since $R = TT^+$

$$WT = T(T^+WT) = T\epsilon \quad \dots (3)$$

which is really Harris' pseudo-eigenvalue equation. Diagonalisation of W, however, seldom leads to convergence. This may be, as McWeeny pointed out⁵, due to the fact that such an eigenvalue equation uses a wrong energy surface. The change in R corresponding to a steepest descent of the energy surface is given by¹

$$\delta R = -\lambda L - \lambda^2 LM \quad \dots (4)$$

where $N = \frac{\text{tr}LW}{2(\text{tr}LW - \text{tr}LMW)}$

$$L = s + s^+, M = s - s^+$$

$$s = (1-R)WR, \text{ and } N_{ij} = -2\omega\beta_0 L_{ij} \delta_{ij}$$

The correction leads to the best 1-descent approximation to R and E. The iterative process is continued until self-consistency is achieved. As the convergence of the method seemed very good indeed introduction of any more sophistication like the conjugate gradient technique, etc., into the method is deemed unnecessary. The method thus seems very simple yet promises to give very good charge density distribution.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1 we give the values of dipole moments of some non-benzenoids calculated by the above method along with results obtained by other methods. Experimental values are rare and one has to compare with other theoretical values. As the skeletal formulae of these compounds are simple and wellknown, we avoid depicting them for brevity. We have used the bond-lengths and -angles given by Birss and Dasgupta⁶, Dasgupta and Dasgupta⁷

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF SOME NON-BENZENOID COMPOUNDS (in Debye unit)

Non-Benzenoid	Hückel method	ω -technique	SCF ω -technique	SCF method	Experimental value
1. Fulvene	4.75	2.70	1.96		1.2 ^x
2. Azulene	6.41	4.70	1.99	1.79 ^a 2.20 ^b 2.20 ^c 2.74 ^d	1.0 ^x
3. Acepleiadylene	8.47	6.89	5.30	1.15 ^a 2.06 ^b	0.5 ^y
4. Naphth (cde) azulene	5.93	4.53	3.64	1.71 ^a 1.70 ^b	—
5. Pentaleno (def) heptalene	5.74	4.45	3.40	1.68 ^a 1.51 ^b	—
6. Cyclohept (bc) acenaphthylene	4.37	3.47	2.67	0.60 ^a 0.87 ^b	—
7. Cyclohept'a (def) fluorene	10.09	8.10	4.39	4.28 ^a 4.00 ^b 3.54 ^c 4.25 ^d	—

a : D. H. Lo and M. A. Whitehead—*Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 2027.

b : A. L. H. Chung and M. J. S. Dewar—*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 756.

c : M. J. S. Dewar and A. J. Harget—*Proc. Roy. Soc. London*, 1970, **A315**, 443, 457.

d : H. Yamaguchi, T. Nakajima and T. L. Kuni, *Theor. Chim. Acta. Berl.*, 1968, **12**, 349.

x : C. W. Wheland and D. E. Mann, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, **17**, 264.

y : D. A. Pitt, A. J. Petro and C. P. Smyth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 5633.

where the skeletal formulae are also to be found. It has been found that the number of cycles needed for self-consistency for a compound is less than that required in the conventional ω -technique. Harris's method never converged with $\omega=1.4$ and seldom did so with other values of ω . It is really gratifying to note that the dipole moment values calculated by the present method are a lot better than those obtained by Hückel method and conventional ω -technique and in some cases are comparable to those obtained by more sophisticated pi-electron calculations where two electron interactions have been considered. This observation amply justifies our contention that the correct self-consistent charge distributions have been obtained by the present method and hence the dipole moment values are the

best possible ones obtainable within the Hückel approximation and for the given geometries.

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